

How to use and maintain refrigeration products

Energy efficient refrigeration products will help to significantly reduce the energy costs. The smart designing of the refrigeration product components reduces the installation and maintenance costs, and saves your valuable time and money.

Evaporators are commonly known as freezers in the domestic refrigerators. It is a main part of the refrigeration system as they act as heat exchangers that transfer heat to the refrigerant to get it cooled. They are considered as an important part of the refrigeration system as they transfer heat from the substance to the refrigerant. Evaporators are used in diverse applications and are available in a wide variety of shapes, sizes and designs. In large refrigeration systems, they are used for chilling the water.

Condensing units that are energy efficient, reliable and can be easily installed are a preferable option in various restaurants, hospitals, canteens, cooling rooms, fermentation rooms etc. They can be cleaned with commercial coil cleaners available for its proper maintenance. They are an assembly of different components like condensers, motors, compressors, controls etc.

Bin Dasmal General Trading, a part of Bin Dasmal Group supplies the refrigeration products of various US and European brands in the GCC region. The product range includes product such as include Coatings, Adhesives, Sealants, Thermal Insulation, Copper Pipes, Compressors, Condensers, Evaporators, Controls, and much more. Moreover, these products are of globally leading brands such as Foster®, Aeroflex, Dorin, Friga-Bohn, Danfoss, Lawton, Klea-Mexichem, Garmco and more. The Company is one of the reputed [refrigeration product suppliers in UAE](#) with a key focus on product quality and affordable pricing. Innovative products and ethical business practices sets them apart from their competitors in the GCC region. Bin Dasmal Group reliably and competently supports its customers with experienced and trained technical team.